

Introduction

We are dedicated to fostering a welcoming and inclusive community for members of all backgrounds and career stages across Africa. This Code of Conduct outlines the principles and expectations for respectful and inclusive interaction within the AREN community and across our network. Adhering to this Code of Conduct will help us all contribute to a thriving and supportive environment for open science in Africa.

By being a member of our community, network, or participating in AREN's activities, you agree to adhere to this Code.

Purpose

The purpose of this Code of Conduct is to:

- Foster a welcoming and respectful environment where all individuals feel valued, regardless of their background, identity, or perspective.
- Encourage ethical conduct in all AREN-related activities, including research, collaboration, and communication.
- Prohibit any form of harassment, discrimination, or bullying based on race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, gender identity, religion, disability, age, or any other characteristic.
- Promote fair and equitable treatment of all individuals involved in AREN activities.

Applicability and Scope:

This Code of Conduct applies to all members of the AREN community, regardless of location, and to all online and in-person AREN events, platforms and communications. This includes, but is not limited to:

- AREN [and any externally associated] websites, online forums and community hubs
- AREN [and any externally associated] social media channels
- Email and other modes of communication by AREN
- In-person events such as workshops and conferences

Expected Behavior

All AREN members are expected to:

- Treat all individuals with dignity and respect, avoiding any form of harassment, discrimination, or bullying.
- Foster open and transparent communication, sharing information and ideas constructively and respectfully.
- Work collaboratively with others, valuing diverse perspectives and contributions.

- Adhere to the highest ethical standards in all AREN-related activities, including presentations, research, resource sharing, and publication.
- Respect intellectual property rights and avoid plagiarism or unauthorized use of others' work.
- Report any violations of this Code of Conduct to the appropriate authorities.

Prohibited Behaviour

The following behaviours are strictly prohibited and will not be tolerated:

- Any form of harassment, discrimination, or bullying, including but not limited to:
 - Verbal harassment: Insults, threats, or offensive language.
 - Physical harassment: Unwanted physical contact, intimidation, or aggression.
 - Sexual harassment: Unwelcome sexual advances, requests for sexual favours, or other verbal or physical conduct of a sexual nature.
 - Cyberbullying: The use of electronic communication to bully or harass others.
- Any behaviour that disrupts AREN activities or creates a hostile environment.
- Engaging in activities that could compromise the integrity of AREN or its members.
 - Financial Conflicts of Interest: Disclosing and managing any financial interests that could influence decision-making or performance of responsibilities.
 - Personal Conflicts of Interest: Situations that could lead to bias or favouritism.
- Misusing AREN resources, such as funding, or intellectual property.

Consequences of Unacceptable Behaviour

Members who engage in unacceptable behaviour will be asked to stop immediately. Depending on the severity of the violation, consequences may include:

- A private reprimand such as warnings from the team, event organisers or moderators.
- A public announcement of the incident.
- A temporary or permanent ban from AREN platforms and events.
- Reporting the incident to relevant authorities when deemed necessary.

Reporting Violations:

If you experience or witness a violation of this Code of Conduct, please report it to AREN immediately. You can report an incident by:

- Emailing us at team@africanrn.org

- Contacting a member of the AREN leadership team directly
- Submitting an anonymous report through the incident report form

Resolution and Enforcement Process

The AREN Team will review all reports of unacceptable behaviour and ensure a fair and impartial review process. All reports will be taken seriously and investigated promptly. The team will determine appropriate consequences for violations. The Team may establish a Review Group for complex cases.

- Upon receiving a report, the AREN Team will confirm receipt and gather information.
- Depending on the situation, the Team may take immediate action to protect safety.
- The Team or Review Group will determine if the Code of Conduct was violated.
- Possible resolutions include reprimands, announcements, suspensions, or bans.
- The reporter will be kept informed throughout the process.

Confidentiality and Appeals:

The AREN Team and any Review Group will respect the confidentiality of reporting parties to the best of our ability. Only those with a strict need to know will have access to this information. However, we may be required to disclose information in certain circumstances, such as to ensure the safety of individuals or comply with legal obligations.

Appeals of enforcement decisions can be submitted to the AREN leadership team.

Conflicts of Interest

In the event of any conflict of interest (a Team member, their family member, or someone with whom the Team member has a close academic, personal or employment relationship is involved in a complaint), the Team member must immediately notify the other members, and recuse themselves if necessary.

Review and Updates

This Code of Conduct will be reviewed and updated periodically to ensure its continued relevance and effectiveness. We encourage feedback from the community.

Acknowledgements:

This Code of Conduct is adapted from several existing community codes, including the UKRN Code of Conduct and the eLife Code of Conduct.